

School, Parents, and Community Support on Pupils' Academic Success during the New Normal

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Abstract— One of the major effects of the COVID-19 pandemic is the sudden shift to distance learning among basic education schools in the country. With this, stakeholders play a critical role in helping pupils cope with the demands of the said modality. This study was conducted to determine the school, parents, and community support in the new normal and their relationship to pupils' academic success in Alcala East District, Division of Cagayan for the School Year 2020-2021. A mixed method of research was utilized employing both quantitative and qualitative research designs. A stratified random sampling was used in this study to determine the total number of participants from Grades 4 – 6. The results revealed that the extent of support of the school and the parents for pupil's academic success was to a moderate extent. Meanwhile, the extent of support of the community for pupil's academic success was low. Furthermore, there is no significant difference on the extent of support of the parents in terms of the profile variables. Moreover, pupil-participants had a moderate level of motivation in learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. There was also a moderately favorable attitude of pupils in modular learning in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, the academic performance of pupils in modular learning approached proficiency with a mean grade of 81.01. In addition, there is a significant relationship between the extent of support of the school, parents, and the community and the level of academic success of pupils in terms of motivation, attitude towards learning, and overall academic performance. Results of the qualitative data revealed four major problems encountered by pupils in modular distance learning which include the following: (1) lack of academic support, (2) poor internet and mobile connection, (3) physical and mental stress, and (4) overloaded lesson activities. The study concludes that school, parents, and community support for pupils' academic success during the new normal is important.

Keywords— *Academic Achievement, Community Support, Distance Learning, Learning Attitude, Learning Motivation, Parent Support, School Support*

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on every aspect of society, including educational systems around the world. Home confinement was one of the most severe restrictive measures imposed by national governments around the world to contain the spread of the new coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2). This action

has resulted in a one-time, temporary suspension of teaching activities.

This learning crisis is being exacerbated by the COVID-19 crisis. Around the world, up to 94% of the children have been absent from school due to closures (Azevedo, et. al., 2021). Inequities, particularly for students who have already been left behind by education systems, exacerbate learning losses associated with school closures (Vlachos, et. al., 2021). Numerous countries and schools have shifted to online learning as a stop-gap measure during school closures. This, however, is not always possible, as less than half of households in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) have access to the internet. To minimize disruption and ensure that students could receive instruction remotely during school closures, teachers and schools implemented new strategies such as distance learning programs and open educational applications and platforms. As a result, the Department of Education pioneered distance education. Distance Learning is a mode of instruction in which learning occurs between the teacher and learners are geographically separated during instruction. This mode of instruction is classified into three distinct categories: modular distance learning (MDL), online distance learning (ODL), and television/radio-based instruction (Quinones, 2020). In most cases, schools implement modular distance learning due to internet issues and concerns especially among rural areas and provinces in the country.

In this regard, parent support is critical, particularly for younger students who are not yet fully self-sufficient in managing their assigned learning activities (Wang, 2020). These strategies, however, raised concerns because not all parents were able to work alongside their children, and not every household had the necessary electronic devices, such as laptops with wi-fi connections (Zaccoletti, et. al., 2020; Nikolopoulou, 2020). Furthermore, it is well understood that school and home are two distinct environments in which students must perform different tasks. Students, on the other hand, have found themselves without physical contact with either their teachers or their classmates in this situation. In addition, in this new normal of education, it is also important that other stakeholders be involved in the education of pupils such as the school and the community.

Partnerships between families, schools, and communities are a shared responsibility and mutual process in which schools

and other community agencies and organizations engage families in meaningful and culturally appropriate ways, and families take the initiative to actively support their children's development and learning (De Jesus, 2021; Karisa, 2020). Additionally, schools and community organizations make an effort to listen to parents, support them, and equip them with the tools necessary to be active partners in their children's education. Partnerships are critical for students to achieve their full potential, and while parent and community involvement has always been a cornerstone of public education, there is a need for increased recognition and support of the value of these collaborative efforts (Cochran, 2020). This is true especially among public schools in the Philippines. With the implementation of the distance-based education due to the COVID-19 pandemic, it is important to assess school, parents, and community support to the education of pupils and their relationship to pupil's learning achievement, such as in Jurisdiccio Elementary School in Alcala, Cagayan. As part of the teaching force, the researcher observed that there were some inconsistencies regarding how these three stakeholders support the education of pupils. Hence, this study is conducted. public.

II. METHODS

This study utilized both quantitative and qualitative types of research to determine the extent of support of the parents, school and community on pupils' academic success during the new normal. Specifically, a descriptive-correlational research design was used in this study. Descriptive research design was used to determine the profile of the participants, extent of support of the parents, school and community on the pupils' academic success, and level of academic success of pupils. Meanwhile, correlational research method was used to determine significant relationship between the level of academic success and the extent of support by the school, parents, and community. Meanwhile, for the qualitative aspect, the researcher utilized basic qualitative design by Merriam (2016) to explore the problems encountered by pupils with regard to the extent of support given by parents, teachers, and community in the new normal.

The participants of the study were the Grade 4-6 pupils of Jurisdiccio Elementary School in District of Alcala, Division of Cagayan. Participants were selected based on to their level of comprehension and understanding to the certain study. They were also selected using the following exclusion and inclusion criteria: (1) must be a grade 4-6 pupil and (2) must submit a parent's consent affirming to be part of the study.

This study utilized a questionnaire with four parts to determine the extent of support of the parents, school, and community on pupils' academic success during the new normal. The data were analyzed and interpreted using descriptive statistics,

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extent of Support on the Pupil's Academic Success

Table 1. Extent of Support of the School on the Pupils' Academic Success

Items	Mean	Qualitative Description
Teachers do home visitation to ensure that learning takes place despite the current educational set-up.	2.42	low extent
Teachers monitor their pupils especially with regard to their progress in accomplishing the tasks provided in the SLMs.	3.10	moderate extent
Teachers and the school are always available for communication, feed-backing and inquiries	3.42	great extent
The school implements intervention and remediation programs to address pupils' issues concerning their studies	3.05	moderate extent
I receive the academic support from the school needed to support my needs.	3.05	moderate extent
Despite the pandemic, the school still give recognitions to students for their exemplary performance.	2.51	low extent
The school made an effort to collaborate with other agencies for funding and support for pupil's education.	3.02	moderate extent
Teachers do occasional conversations with pupils throughout the modular learning so they would know their learning progress.	3.24	moderate extent
Teachers work hand-in-hand with parents in education such as monitoring, giving instructions and evaluating pupil's academic progress.	3.24	moderate extent
The school established a network of communication among stakeholders such as parents for support at home is easy.	3.12	moderate extent
Category Mean	3.01	moderate extent

Table 1 shows the extent of support of the school on the pupils' academic success. Specifically, it can be seen from the table that the highest item being assessed by the participants is "teachers and the school are always available for communication, feed-backing, and inquiries" with a mean of 3.42 with a qualitative description of great extent. Accordingly, strong parent-teacher connectedness leads to academic gains for students: higher grades and test scores, better attendance, and participation, and decreased behavioral problems in the classroom (Guan & Benavides, 2021; Mann & Gilmore, 2021; Garbacz, et al., 2021). In addition, the findings of the current study are the same with the results of recent studies stressing the importance of communication between school and parents to respond to the needs of

children in the midst of the pandemic (Muckenthaler, et al., 2020; Honigsfeld & Nordmeyer, 2020).

Meanwhile, majority of the items were assessed by the participants to a moderate extent. Specifically, participants observed that teachers sometimes monitor their pupils especially with regard to their progress in accomplishing the tasks provided in the SLMs, hence, the school is sometimes implementing intervention and remediation programs to address pupils' issues concerning their studies, and they sometimes receive the academic support from the school needed to support their needs. The findings are the same with recent studies stressing that schools and teachers have moderate extent of support to children in the midst of the pandemic (Bartolome, et al., 2020; Tudy & Gauran-Tudy, 2020). Meanwhile, Chin et al. (2020) claimed that this may be attributed to the idea that in the midst of the pandemic, the school needs to adjust and cope with the demands of distance learning. And with that, teachers are bombarded with a lot of responsibilities and functions that they need to attend to. Hence, pupils may not also be conscious in looking into the other major functions of teachers and the school.

And finally, two items were assessed by the participants to a low extent. These include the following: teachers are doing home visitation to ensure that learning takes place despite the current educational set-up and the school still give recognitions to students for their exemplary performance.

In general, participants assessed the support given by the school in the education of children in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic to a moderate extent with a mean of 3.02. This means that the school offers some activities and initiatives to strengthen their support with their pupils. However, the extent of engagement is not that high. This is supported by studies conducted by Chan (2021) and Bautista, et al. (2021).

Table 2. Extent of Support of the Parents on the Pupils' Academic Success

Items	Mean	Qualitative Description
Parents are able to receive and return the self-learning modules on time	3.75	great extent
Parents are able to encourage their children to learn at home.	3.57	great extent
Parents have the capacity to facilitate the modular learning session for their children.	3.08	moderate extent
Parents and other members of the family help the child in understanding the SLMS.	3.14	moderate extent
Parents are available to mentor the child with regard to his/her modular classes.	3.10	moderate extent
Parents provide materials and resources for learning tasks done at home.	3.08	moderate extent
Parents help and assist their children to	3.06	moderate

make projects at home.		extent
Parents guide their children in doing activities and even experiments.	3.03	moderate extent
Parents can easily communicate to my teachers if there are some unclarified instructions.	2.83	moderate extent
Parents can manage to help learn while looking for ways to earn.	3.05	moderate extent
Category Mean	3.17	moderate extent

Table 12 shows the extent of support of the parents on the pupils' academic success. Specifically, two items were assessed by the participants to a great extent. These include the following: parents are able to receive and return the self-learning modules on time and parents are able to encourage their children to learn at home with means of 3.75 and 3.57 respectively. With the shift to distance learning, there are additional responsibilities given to parents to help in the education of their children which encourage them to study at home through different modes of learning such as modules, TV, and even radio-based instruction. Accordingly, parents serve as home facilitators and para-teachers who facilitate and guide the students in answering the modular lessons they sent during the modular learning (Manlangit et al. 2020). Depending on the administrators' schedules, parents and guardians pick up the school's self-learning modules (DepEd, 2020). In the new normal, parents have to play a more significant role in the learning and development of their child than they have done traditionally. More so, because most education is now taking place in the home environment instead of the school campus, without the physical presence of teachers.

Meanwhile, all the other items were rated by the participants to a moderate extent. These include the following: Parents have the capacity to facilitate the modular learning session for their children, Parents and other members of the family help the child in understanding the SLMS, Parents are available to mentor the child with regards to his/her modular classes, Parents provide materials and resources for learning tasks done at home, Parents help and assist their children to make projects at home, Parents guide their children in doing activities and even experiments, Parents can easily communicate to my teachers if there are some unclarified instructions and parents can manage to help learn while looking for ways to earn. Cahapay (2021) stressed that school closures put more responsibilities on the parents' shoulders, thus, most of the parents in the study shared that they thought that they had enough resources available. Meanwhile, Apriyanti (2020) stressed that there are some hindrances and obstacles that affect the involvement and support of parents in the education of their children that is why they cannot provide maximum support to the education children. Furthermore, Garbe (2020) stressed that parents described having difficulties with balancing responsibilities, learner motivation, accessibility, and learning outcomes. In general, the extent of support of the

parents on the pupil's academic success is in moderate extent with a category mean of 3.20.

Table 3. Extent of Support of the Community on the Pupils' Academic Success

Items	Mean	Qualitative Description
The community and other stakeholders support the pupils in education by providing assistance such as load allowance, provision of internet, and other important educational resources and materials.	1.95	low extent
The community imposes some ordinances, rules and policies governing the implementation of the modular learning.	2.25	low extent
Financial support is always available in the barangay.	1.94	low extent
There is an available learning resource area put-up by the community to support the education of pupils in the midst of the pandemic.	2.00	low extent
The community organizes educational-related programs and activities to support the education of pupils during the pandemic.	2.03	low extent
The community offers other activities to cater to the needs in the normal education such as provision of transportation, devices for learning, and others.	2.02	low extent
The community also assists in the different activities initiated by the school such as enrolment, distribution, and retrievals of SLMS, etc.	2.90	moderate extent
The community also provides learning materials readily available to learners, and even to parents.	2.09	low extent
The community provides trainings for parents for them to adapt to the new normal of education while observing the required health protocols for COVID-19.	2.02	low extent
Private sectors also support in modular learning.	2.91	moderate extent
Category Mean	2.21	low extent

Table 3 shows the extent of support of the community on the pupils' academic success. It can be seen from the results that the highest two items being assessed by participants are the following: private sectors also support in modular learning and the community also assists in the different activities initiated by the school such as enrolment, distribution, and retrievals of SLMS, etc. with means of 2.91 and 2.90, respectively with qualitative description of moderate. The findings confirm the results of recent studies stressing on the low level of support given by the community and other sectors in the education of children in distance learning (Dewi & Wajdi, 2021; Hart, 2021; Dianito, et al., 2021). In addition, Rosales and Pagsuyoin (2021) stressed

that private sectors are usually the ones helping schools in times of needs such as providing educational and learning materials, health and sanitation kits, and other materials and their extensive support also extends to the school even before the COVID-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, the community through the Barangay Council also plays a critical role in the success of learning in the midst the pandemic. According to Palad (2022), barangay council members play the lead role or the main character in the distribution of modules, and as bridge between the school/teachers and the students. It is important to note that almost all of the items were assessed by the participants as low. The participants observed that the community is not that active in helping in the distance education of children. According to Carlet et al. (2020), barangay council members may have a limited support to the school and children since they also have other important things that need to do such as COVID-19 mitigation and even recovery.

Level of Academic Success of the Pupils

Table 4. Level of Academic Success of the Pupils in terms of Motivation.

Motivation	Mean	Qualitative Description
Intrinsic Goal Orientation		
I prefer SLMs that really challenge me, so I can learn new things.	2.39	Low
I prefer SLMs that arouse my curiosity, even if it's difficult to learn.	2.42	Low
The most satisfying thing for me is trying to understand the content of SLMs as thoroughly as possible.	2.66	Moderate
I choose learning tasks that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	2.47	Low
Mean	2.48	Low
Extrinsic Goal Orientation		
Getting a good grade in the new normal education is the most satisfying thing for me	2.88	Moderate
The most important thing for me is to improve my overall grade point average, so my concern is getting a good grade.	2.90	Moderate
I want to get better grades than most of the other pupils	2.86	Moderate
I want to do well in my modular classes because it's important to show my ability to my family, friends, or others	3.11	Moderate
Mean	2.92	Moderate
Control of Learning Beliefs		
If I study in appropriate ways, then I'll be able to learn the material	3.23	Moderate
It's my own fault if I don't learn the material taught.	3.19	Moderate
If I try hard enough, then I'll understand the material presented.	3.23	Moderate
If I don't understand the material presented, it's because I didn't try hard enough.	3.14	Moderate

Mean	3.20	Moderate
Self-Efficacy		
I believe I'll receive excellent grades in my modular class.	2.31	Low
I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the SLMs.	2.30	Low
I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts that are reflected in the SLMs.	2.54	Low
I'm confident I can understand the most complex material presented in the module.	2.22	Low
I'm confident I can do an excellent job on assignments and tests.	2.34	Low
I expect to do well.	2.33	Low
Considering the difficulty of the new set-up brought by the COVID-19, I think I can do well	2.30	Low
Mean	2.33	Low
Task Value		
I think I will be able to use what I learn in SLMs.	3.02	Moderate
It is important for me to learn the course material.	3.00	Moderate
I am very interested in the content area of the module.	2.89	Moderate
I think the course material in modular class is useful for me to learn.	3.08	Moderate
I like the subject matters in the modular learning.	2.86	Moderate
Understanding the subject matter is very important to me.	2.99	Moderate
Mean	2.97	Moderate
Learning Engagement		
I still feel connected from my teacher, despite the situation.	3.12	Moderate
I enjoy answering tasks in my modules.	2.90	Moderate
I pay attention in what my parents and even teachers say.	3.15	Moderate
Mean	3.05	Moderate
Category Mean	2.83	Moderate

Table 4 shows the level of academic success of the pupils in terms of motivation. As shown in the table, one of the most important components of learning in every context is motivation that initiates and sustains behavior. It can be revealed from the results that pupil-participants have a low level of intrinsic motivation with a mean of 2.48. As a result, when it comes to learning on their own in learning environments, the level of intrinsic motivation sparks and sustains the interest of open and distance education pupils (Adedigba & Sulaiman, 2020; Stojanovic, et al., 2021; Bhure, et al., 2021). Along intrinsic goal motivation, it can be shown that three out of four indicators on motivation had low level. According to Jong (2020), pupils are not intrinsically motivated in learning because they do not have enough avenues to learn and to show their skills and talents since they are limited to SLMs and only learning in their homes.

Meanwhile, participants have assessed their academic success along extrinsic goal orientation to a

moderate extent with mean of 2.92. Furthermore, the table further shows that pupils have moderate level of learning motivation along control of learning beliefs with a mean 3.20. Control belief about learning refers to students' beliefs about the contingency between their behaviors and their performance as well as learning concerns on how much perceived control one has to accomplish positive and desired outcomes (Mandelbaum, 2020). On one hand, pupils have a low level of learning motivation along self-efficacy with a mean of 2.33 because accordingly, parents are the ones doing the learning tasks of their children because pupils are not that motivated in learning. Pupils believe that cannot they receive excellent grades in their classes since they cannot understand some materials presented in their SLMs and they are not also confident in learning even basic concepts that are reflected in their said platform (Luaña, 2021; Olivo, 2021). Along task-value, the level of motivation of pupil-participants was at moderate extent with a mean of 2.97. This could mean that they feel that the things that they learned in their modules are important in their lives. However just in a moderate extent. According to expectancy-value theory, task value includes positive components such as intrinsic, attainment, and utility values and negative ones. The term task value indicates that the construct was developed to describe the motivation of a person to engage in a specific task. And finally, in terms of learner engagement, pupil-participants have a moderate level of learning motivation with a mean of 3.15. This could mean that pupils still find ways to be engaged in their learning by connecting with their teachers and also asking for assistance from their parents. In general, pupil-participants have a moderate level of motivation in learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 5. *Level of Academic Success of the Pupils in terms of Attitude towards Learning*

Attitude towards Learning	Mean	Qualitative Description
Answering Learning Tasks in the Modules		
It is easy for me to answer learning tasks and activities of my modules.	2.24	Less Favorable
I enjoy answering learning tasks and activities in the modules.	2.72	Moderately Favorable
I have control when to answer learning tasks and activities.	2.81	Moderately Favorable
I am interested, engaged, and motivated whenever I answer learning tasks in my modules.	2.77	Moderately Favorable
I have flexibility and many opportunities engaging with my SLMs	2.62	Moderately Favorable
Mean	2.63	Moderately Favorable
Communicating with Teachers		
It is easy to communicate with my teacher	2.88	Moderately Favorable
It is useful to communicate with	3.18	Moderately Favorable

my teacher		Favorable
I enjoy communicating with my teacher	3.04	Moderately Favorable
I have control when to communicate with my teacher	2.98	Moderately Favorable
I am interested (engaged, motivated) when I Communicate with my teacher.	3.02	Moderately Favorable
I have flexibility and many opportunities to Communicate with my teacher	2.81	Moderately Favorable
Mean	2.98	Moderately Favorable
Collaborating with Classmates		
It is easy to Collaborate with my peers (classmates).	2.83	Moderately Favorable
It is useful to Collaborate with my peers (classmates).	2.89	Moderately Favorable
I enjoy collaborating with my peers (classmates)	2.90	Moderately Favorable
I have control when to Collaborate with my peers (classmates)	2.89	Moderately Favorable
I am interested (engaged, motivated) when I Communicate with my peers (classmates).	2.95	Moderately Favorable
I have flexibility and many opportunities to Collaborate with my peers (classmates).	2.81	Moderately Favorable
Mean	2.88	Moderately Favorable
Category Mean	2.83	Moderately Favorable

Table 5 shows the level of academic success of the pupils in terms of attitude towards learning. It can be shown from the results that in terms of answering learning tasks in the modules, pupil-participants had a moderately favorable attitude with a mean of 2.63. This indicates that pupils have either a favorable or unfavorable attitude towards answering learning tasks in their modules. This may be attributed to the fact that modular learning is flexible that they can answer their learning tasks whenever they want, hence this may affect their ways of answering their given tasks. It is important to note that recent studies conducted show that many pupils seem disinterested in modular learning. Students may no longer have an internet connection, a device to use, or a space to learn in. Some students may not be available to meet at specific times. Others may have a lot going on in the background that they're trying to block out or even hide from the rest of the class (Castroverde & Acala, 2021; Wijanarko, et al., 2020).

Meanwhile, in terms of communicating with their teachers, pupil participants had a moderately favorable attitude with a mean of 2.98. This suggests that pupils sometimes communicate with their teachers with regard to their lessons. In light of the study of Gueta and Janer (2021), communication with teachers should be one of the major responsibilities of pupils since modular learning is primarily an independent kind of learning. And finally, pupil-

participants had a moderately favorable attitude towards communicating with their classmates with a mean of 2.88. The findings is in congruent with the recent studies stressing a moderately favorable attitude of pupils in modular learning in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic (Capinding, 2022; Garay-Arandoña, et al., 2022).

Table 6. Level of Academic Success of the Pupils in terms of Overall Academic Performance

Academic Performance	Frequency	Percentage
90 and above	38	43.00
85-89	34	38.70
80-84	11	14.00
74 and below	4	4.30
Total	87	100.00
Mean Grade	80.96	Approaching Proficiency

Table 23 shows the level of academic success of pupils in terms of their overall academic performance. It can be shown from the table that many of them got 90 and above grades in modular learning with 38 pupils of 43%. This finding is supported by the results of recent studies stressing the high academic performance of students and pupils in modular learning (Catroverde & Alcala, 2021; Dargo & Dimas, 2021; Barcenas & Bibon, 2022). However, generally, the academic performance of pupils in modular learning is approaching proficiency with a mean grade of 81.01.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Academic Success and the Extent of Support

Table 7. Significant Relationship between the Level of Academic success and the Extent of School Support

Variables	Pearson-R	P-value	Decision
School Support and Motivation	0.53	0.00	Reject Ho
School Support and Attitude towards Learning	0.55	0.00	Reject Ho
School Support and Overall Academic Performance	0.33	0.00	Reject Ho

Table 24 shows the significant relationship between the level of academic success and the extent of school support. These were supported by the probability values of .00, .00, and .00 respectively. It can be shown from the table that there is a significant relationship between the extent of support and the level of academic success of pupils in terms of motivation, attitude towards learning, and overall academic performance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that the extent of support given by the school positively influences pupils' academic success in the midst of distance learning. The findings are in congruent with the results of previous studies stressing on the positive

effect of high school support in the academic performance of pupils (Tus, 2020; Ferraces Otero, et al., 2021).

Table 7. Significant Relationship between the Level of Academic Success and the Extent of Parent’s Support

Variables	Pearson-R	P-value	Decision
Parent’s Support and Motivation	0.83	0.00	Reject Ho
Parent’s Support and Attitude towards Learning	0.55	0.00	Reject Ho
Parent’s Support and Overall Academic Performance	0.69	0.00	Reject Ho

Table 7 shows the significant relationship between the level of academic success and the extent of parent’s support. It can be shown from the results that there is a significant relationship between the level of academic success in terms of motivation, attitude towards learning and overall academic performance and the extent of parent’s support. These were supported by the probability values of .00, .00, and .00 respectively. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the extent of support given by parents to the education of their children positive influences pupils’ academic success. Findings from the present study demonstrated that increased parent support was significantly related to increased academic performance. Accordingly, if parent-child involvement has any tangible benefits, it likely leads to higher educational expectations, reduced truancy, minimized absenteeism, and an increased focus on homework – which theoretically increases academic achievement (Choi, 2021; Gunzenhauser, et al., 2021; Dejarlo, et al., 2020).

Table 8. Significant Relationship between the Level of Academic Success and the Extent of Community Support

Variables	Pearson-R	P-value	Decision
Community Support and Motivation	0.83	0.00	Reject Ho
Community Support and Attitude towards Learning	0.55	0.00	Reject Ho
Community Support and Overall Academic Performance	0.09	0.37	Accept Ho

Table 26 shows the significant relationship between the level of academic success and the extent of community support. It can be gleaned from the table that there is a significant relationship between the level of academic success in terms of motivation and attitude towards learning and the extent of community support both with probability values of .00. This means that the support given by the community on the education of children in the midst of the pandemic positively influences pupils’ motivation and attitude towards learning. This is supported by the study of Shaturaev (2021) that community support is a factor for student achievement because the community offers in

helping achieve a conducive learning space. However, there is no significant relationship between the level of academic success in terms of overall academic performance and the extent of community support. This is supported by the findings of Wilke (2021) and Harmon, e t al. (2021).

Problems Encountered by the Participants during the New Normal

Results of the qualitative data revealed four major problems encountered by pupils in modular distance learning which include the following: (1) lack of academic support, (2) poor internet and mobile connection, (3) physical and mental stress, and (4) overloaded lesson activities.

1. Lack of Academic Support

This was the major issue and concern of pupils in new normal education in which they claimed that because of this kind of set-up, they find difficulty in learning difficult lessons especially in Mathematics and Science since their parents had limited knowledge with regard to this subject matter. In addition, another aspect of the lack of academic support focused on the limited and inadequate learning resources available at home. Hence, they only relied on the SLMs given to them.

2. Poor Internet and Mobile Connection

Another issue that pupil-participants experienced in the new normal education was poor internet and mobile connection. According to participants, their location did not have a good internet and mobile signal that they could use to communicate with their teachers and even to their classmates. In addition, due to limited internet connection, they found it difficult to access some electronic learning materials that would aid their learning.

3. Physical and Mental Stress

Due to limited social interaction and their prolonged home isolation, pupil-participants said that they experienced physical and mental stress. Some of them stressed that they found it difficult to learn and cope with the demands of modular learning because they felt anxiety and also tiredness.

4. Overloaded Lesson Activities

And finally, overloaded lesson activities were also an issue among pupils. Many of them said that all their modules had learning tasks that they needed to finish and pass to their teachers.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There is a moderate level of support come from the student participants’ school and parents. On the other hand, there is a low level of support coming from the community. The level of motivation and attitudes towards learning by many of the student participants’ is low. Yet, many of them still performed well as manifested in their high academic performance. Furthermore, the level of support that they received from different stakeholders in distance learning

affects their learning motivation, attitude, and their overall academic performance. Finally, pupils experienced some difficulties and challenges in modular learning in new normal education.

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